

Differing Interpretations of the Lagrangian in Classical and Quantum Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Nov. 3. 2021

Classical mechanics, which is a deterministic theory, was developed largely with the work of Newton. Later, the Lagrangian approach of obtaining stationary paths of an action was introduced to obtain the Newtonian results. Thus a deterministic theory was considered in the interpretation of varying paths in the action with the stationary path being the classical mechanical result. In (1) we have argued that both relativistic and nonrelativistic quantum mechanics follow from varying x and t independently in $v = x/t = \text{constant}$ in the classical action for a free particle with constant momentum. In this case, it seems one considers a fluctuating distance or a stochastic approach, yet in this note we argue that for $d\text{Action}/dx = p$ for the quantum case is very similar to $dL/dv = p$ for the classical. It is the interpretation which seems to differ. We argue that an energy flow through space i.e. a p in quantum mechanics seems to follow from a certain kind of spatial probability fluctuation i.e. a periodic one. On average the free particle case and also the bound state case yield classical results so the Lagrangian approach of classical mechanics is linked to quantum rms values.

Independent x and t in the Classical Free Particle Action

It has been shown in (1) that for both the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions that:

$$d\text{Action}/dx \text{ (partial)} = p \quad \text{and} \quad d\text{Action}/dt \text{ (partial)} = -E \quad ((1a)) \quad ((1b))$$

In other words Action = time * Lagrangian, $v = x/t$ is used and x and t varied independently. From these one may use an energy conservation equation e.g. $E = pp/2m$ or $EE = pp + m_0 c^2$ (for a free particle) and obtain the Schrodinger or Klein-Gordon equations.

In this note we wish to investigate more closely the meaning of the independent fluctuations of x and t in v .

Beginning with $d\text{Action}/dx$ one may note that $x \rightarrow x + dx_1$ is similar to $v \rightarrow v + dv$ with $dv = dx_1/dt$. Thus a fluctuation in x holding t constant is similar to a different velocity. Given this idea, we note that ((1a)) may be written as:

$$E(v+dv) - E(v) = p dv \quad ((2)) \quad \text{where } E(v) = .5mv^2 \text{ for the nonrelativistic free particle case.}$$

The relativistic result will be considered later. Given Newtonian mechanics we ask how ((2)) arises. If one considers $v=0$ then $v+dv=dv$. From Newton's second law:

$$dp = p = F dt \quad ((3)) \quad \text{Consider } dv \text{ representing } dx \rightarrow dx + dx_1. \text{ Then:}$$

$$E(v+dv) - E(v) = F (dx + dx_1) - F dx = F dx_1 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{where } F \text{ is considered to be constant in both } dx \text{ and } dx + dx_1 \text{ where } dx_1 \ll dx. \quad ((4)) \text{ is equivalent to:}$$

$$E(v+dv)-E(v) = F dx/dt dt \text{ but from ((4))}$$

$$E(v+dv)-E(v) = p dv \quad ((5))$$

Thus impulses are used to obtain ((5)) or ((2)) and dv is equivalent to a change in dx i.e. a fluctuation which gives the appearance of a dv .

For the case of the classical nonrelativistic free particle action, $dAction/dx = p$, but varying x/t with respect to x is like varying v with respect to dv and $dAction = dt E(v)$ so:

$$dAction/dx = d [E dt] / [dv dt] = dE/dv = p \text{ which is identical to ((5))}$$

Next the relativistic case may be considered. Here $L=Lagrangian = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) so L is not identified with either total energy or kinetic energy in the free particle case. Nevertheless one has (with $m=m_0$):

$$dv \quad dE/dv = \{E(v+dv)-E(v)\} = dv \quad d/dv (m/\sqrt{1-vv}) = m dv / (1-vv)^{3/2}$$

$$\text{From (2): } Fdt = mv/\sqrt{1-vv} \text{ (for } v=0 \text{ changing to } v=dv) \text{ and } Fdx = mv/(1-vv)^{3/2}$$

$$\text{Thus: } Fdt \, dx/dt = (mv/\sqrt{1-vv}) \, dx/dt = (mv/\sqrt{1-vv}) \, dv = dE/dv \, dv$$

where $v=dx/dt$

Once again: $dE = E(v+dv)-E(v) = p \, dv$ but E and p are relativistic results i.e.

$$p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv} \text{ and } E = m/\sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1)$$

Thus a fluctuation in x in the Action is the same as a fluctuation in v and the difference in $E(v+dv)$ and $E(v)$ due to impulses is $p \, dv$. It seems that fluctuations are in a sense creating the energy flow p . As a result, there may be a physical interpretation for

$$-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \text{ and } i d/dt \exp(ipx-iEt) = -1/2m \, d/dx \, d/dx \exp(ipx-iEt)$$

with x and t being independent.

In other words even though one has a constant energy flow p through space one does not consider a deterministic $x(t)$ rather x and t fluctuate in such a way as to create the flow p and they follow $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ which suggests two dimensional motion for both with $\exp(ipx)$ being a kind of probability which moves from one dimension to another in a periodic way (perhaps with one dimension along the p motion and the other in a perpendicular plane because a one dimensional quantum free particle resolves wavelength distances in both directions e.g. the two slit experiment). P or momentum flow is then a kind of average value which is associated with

deterministic motion i.e. $p=mv$ (nonrelativistic) and $v=x/t$ which is deterministic, but is only an average result because periodic fluctuations occur i.e. x and t change independently.

Classical Mechanical dL/dv

Classical mechanical theory follows Newton's equations and is deterministic. The Lagrangian approach is a stationary one which finds a special deterministic path $x(t)$, but here we argue that this is an average type of path because in the previous section we argued one may find E and p ((5)) through fluctuations even though both E and p appear to be deterministic as does $v=x/t$ (v constant).

$p=dL/dv$ in Lagrangian theory. In such a case, one varies velocity in $E=.5mv^2$ (nonrelativistic free particle.) We have argued above, however, that if $v=x/t$ and one varies x and t independently, then a change dx (fluctuation) is like a change dv . The Action= $\int dt L$ where $L=E$ for this special nonrelativistic case.

$$dL/dv = dE/dv = E(v+dv)-E(v) = pdv, \text{ but this is identical to ((5))}$$

The same result holds for the relativistic case as shown in the above section.

Thus both the classical Lagrangian approach and the quantum mechanical approach for a relativistic or nonrelativistic free particle are mathematically the same except they have very different interpretations. For dL/dv one considers only a change in v with $v=x/t$. One does not think in terms of x changing (fluctuating) independently of t . For the quantum case dL/dv is related to $dAction/dx$, but the main idea is that one has independent fluctuations in x and t which give rise to an average p (energy flow) and E . Thus the both the periodic fluctuation scenario and the rms deterministic approach are contained in quantum mechanics with the latter describing classical mechanics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the quantum mechanical result for either a free relativistic or nonrelativistic particle: $dAction/dt=-E$ and $dAction/dx = p$ follow from the idea of impulses for the d/dx equation. Periodic fluctuations i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ give rise to a constant energy flow i.e. p . Thus p is a kind of rms value which follows classical mechanics i.e. $p=mv/\sqrt{1-vv}$, but for quantum mechanics the reality is one of fluctuations. For a bound state quantum system, rms values again follow classical mechanics because $[-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W = KE_{classical}(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction.

Classical Lagrangian theory seeks a stationary solution to variations of: $\int L dt$ i.e. the Action, but this yields an average deterministic result without any notion of fluctuations. We have argued in this note that $p=dL/dv$ from classical Lagrangian theory is identical to $dAction/dx$ and could in fact be interpreted in terms of an x fluctuation, but it is not. Thus it seems that classical mechanics and quantum mechanics are both linked to the classical action, but the interpretation used is very different. Quantum mechanics assumes that x and t are independent in the free

particle relativistic or nonrelativistic classical actions and varies x and t independently in $v=x/t$ leading to $d\text{Action}/dt=-E$ and $d\text{Action}/dx= p$. Using conservation of energy equations one may obtain either the Klein-Gordon or Schrodinger equation.

References

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